

GINGIVAL DEPIGMENTATION: TECHNIQUES, TRENDS AND THERAPEUTIC INSIGHTS

Dr. LEHER SHRIVASTAVA

ABSTRACT

Self-confidence of a person is enhanced with a pristine smile. A harmonious smile has impute shape, colour and position of the teeth with proper gingival margins. Gingival Pigmentation differs with ethnicity of people, which may vary by variety of causes of external and endogenous sources. Melanin pigmentation causes aesthetic concerns and also produces stress. Surgical intervention for such cases is known as Gingival Depigmentation. There are multiple approach in such cases such as lasers, cryosurgery and many more approach are there. The aim of this review is to existing treatment modalities and which give good aesthetic results and low rate of recurrence rate.

Keywords: Melanocytes, Cryosurgery, Depigmentation, Gingival pigmentation Hyperpigmentation, Laser

INTRODUCTION

Dental aesthetic are of the major concern with people. In todays time most important part of ones personality is aesthetics. People are now more conscious of how they look. The position, shape of tooth and the tissue colour plays a vital role in harmonious smile.

Gingival hyperpigmentation can be defined as a darker gingival colour beyond what is normally expected.[1] Pigmentation is contributed by-products of the physiological process such as melanin, melanoid, carotene, oxy haemoglobin, reduced haemoglobin, bilirubin and iron[2] and/or pathological diseases, and conditions.[2] Age and ethnicity also has influence on colour of gingiva but doesn't have and gender prediction.

Different pathological causes of gingival pigmentation are listed in Table. Multiple procedures have been done for gingival pigmentation.

Table 1: Represents the list of various pathological cause of gingival pigmentation

Endocrine diseases	Addison's disease Acromegaly Albright's syndrome Addison's disease Nelson's syndrome
Drug-induced	Quinine Chloroquine Zidovudine Bleomycin

	Minocycline Ketaconazole Cyclophosphamide Chlorpromazine
Heavy metals	Lead Arsenic Bismuth Mercury Silver
Malignant neoplasms	Kaposi's Sarcoma Melanoma
Mucosal conditions	Lichen planus Oral melanoacanthoma Hemochromatosis Blue nevus Nevocellular nevus Hemangiomas HIV oral melanosis Inflammatory mucosal lesions
Tobacco associated	Smoker's melanosis
Idiopathic melanin pigmentation	Peutz-Jegher's syndrome Carney syndrome Leopard syndrome Complex of myxomas
Others	Amalgam tattoo Gingival tattoo Graphite tattoo

GINGIVAL DEPIGMENTATION

Gingival depigmentation can be defined as a periodontal plastic surgical procedure whereby the gingival hyperpigmentation is International removed or reduced by various techniques [3].

Depigmentation is an aesthetic treatment option not a clinical one.

Roshni and Nandakumari [4] in 2005 classified different gingival depigmentation methods as:

1. Methods aimed at removing the pigment layer
 - 1.1 Surgical methods of depigmentation
 - (1.1.1) Scalpel surgical technique:
 - i. Slicing, or partial thickness flap technique
 - ii. Bone Denudation
 - iii. Abrasion
 - iv. Scraping
 - v. Gingivectomy
 - (1.1.2) Cryosurgery

- (1.1.3) Electrosurgery
- (1.1.4) Radiosurgery
- (1.1.5) Lasers

1.2 Chemical method of depigmentation using caustic chemicals,

E.g. 90% phenol.

2. Methods aimed at masking the pigmented gingiva with grafts from less pigmented areas.

2.1 Free gingival grafts (FGG)

2.2 Acellular dermal matrix allografts.

CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF TECHNIQUE

The patient's skin tone, extent of gingival pigmentation, lip contour, upper lip curvature, cosmetic concerns, and treatment expectations influence treatment plan coordination and technique selection. [5, 6, 7]. Treatment should be affordable to the patient and it should not be harming the surrounding tissues of the teeth.

GINGIVAL PIGMENTATION INDEX

An ideal index must be objective and should not depend on the perspective of the examiner. Also, the classifications used in each index must be clear allowing easy determination of the type of pigmentation by the examiner. Moreover, an index must have adequately high validity and reliability and optimal sensitivity and specificity. An ideal index must also be valid, reliable, and reproducible and yield the same result under the same testing conditions. It must be able to classify even small pigmentations and should be acceptable by patients; its use should not cause any discomfort for patients.[8]

There are 5 indices to assess these treatment efficacy. They are as follows:

1. Gingival pigmentation index (GPI)
2. Melanin pigmentation index (MPI)
3. Oral pigmentation index (DOPI)
4. Melanin index (MI)
5. A new index namely the physiologic/pathologic GPI

GPI: Gingival pigmentation index

Zero: No pigmentation

- 1: Brown to black spots
- 2: Brown to black spots without disseminated pigmentation
- 3: Brown to black pigmentation of the marginal and attached gingiva

MPI: Melanin pigmentation index

Zero: No pigmentation

- 1: Separate pigmentation spots in the gingival papilla without extending to the adjacent areas
- 2: Formation of a continuous band of pigmentation with extension to the adjacent areas

DOPI: Dummet's Oral pigmentation index

- 1: No clinical pigmentation
- 2: Mild clinical pigmentation
- 3: Moderate clinical pigmentation
- 4: Severe clinical pigmentation

MI: Melanin index

- 1: No pigmentation
- 2: Presence of one or two separate spots of pigmentation in the gingival papilla without forming a continuous band between the separate pigmentation spots.
- 3: Having more than three separate spots of pigmentation in the gingival papilla without forming a continuous band of pigmentation.
- 4: Presence of one or a few continuous, short bands of pigmentation.
- 5: Presence of a continuous band of pigmentation including the entire inter-canine area

A new index namely the physiologic/pathologic GPI

Currently used GPIs have shortcomings. The severity and the extent of gingival pigmentation should be considered when applying gingival pigmentation index. A binary index to assess and determine gingival pigmentation index for determining the severity band extension of melonotic pigmented lesion, hence it is named as Severity and Extension of Gingival Melonotic Pigmentation Index

Extension of pigmentation based on SEMPI:

- 0: No pigmentation
- 1: Separate pigmented spots in the gingival papilla or marginal gingiva
- 2: Diffused separate pigmented spots
- 3: Separate pigmented patches in the gingival papilla or attached gingiva
- 4: Continuous ribbon-like or diffused patches

Severity of pigmentation based on SEMPI:

- 0: No pigmentation
- 1: Light grey/brown pigmentation

2: Dark brown pigmentation

3: Dark brown/black pigmentation

1.1.1 SCALPEL SURGICAL TECHNIQUE

It was one of the early techniques described to reduce gingival pigmentation and still it remains the most common treatment modality. This procedure basically involves surgical removal of the gingival epithelium along with the underlying connective tissue layer and allowing secondary healing of the exposed connective tissue.

1. Slicing or partial thickness flap technique

Under local anaesthetic infiltration, two incisions are made using this approach, slightly extending the pigmented band's boundaries from the gingival margin to the vestibular area. The surgical area is indicated by these vertical incisions. The epithelium and some connective tissue are carefully separated from one end of the vertical incision using a no. 11 or 15 BP blade held parallel to the gingival surface. It is important to avoid leaving any pigmented remains over the denuded area. Periodontal pack is required after satisfactory hemostasis. Healing is usually uneventful, and complete epithelial healing takes 7 to 14 days. Depigmentation allows for secondary intention healing of denuded connective tissue. As a result, new epithelium forms that lacks melanin pigmentation.[9]

2. Scraping technique

After infiltration of the area with local anaesthesia no.15 or 11 B.P. blade handle is used carefully to scrape off the epithelium along with the underlying pigment layer. The raw surface is irrigated, cleaned and dressings given for 1 week.[10]

Advantages:

1. Economically feasible
2. Does not require any extensive armamentarium
3. Rapid wound healing

Disadvantages:

1. More bleeding during and after surgery
2. Periodontal dressing required
3. Re-pigmentation can occur by migration of active melanocytes from adjacent untreated area {Dummett and Bolden (1963)}

Contraindication:

1. Thin gingival biotype
2. Narrow papillary areas

3. Abrasion

Ginwalla et al. reported the first known case of this method in 1966. It is a reasonably easy, adaptable technique that takes very little time and effort. The technique involves

giving sufficient local anaesthesia before using high speed rotary instruments (round, straight or tapered bur with copious saline irrigation) to de-epithelize pigmented portions of the gingiva. Extensive caution is essential to avoid over pitting of the gingival surface or excessive tissue loss due to rapid speed. The procedure's crudeness, as well as the lack of splatter and aerosol, limits its utilisation. Smaller diamond burs do not easily smooth the surface and have a tendency to generate small pits in the region to be repaired, so larger burs are advised. [11]

Technique:

A medium grit football shaped diamond bur is used at high speeds to denude the epithelium. It takes around 45 min to 1 hour to complete. [Abdel Moneim R et al.]

Advantages:

1. Easy to perform
2. Simple, non-aggressive and safe
3. Less discomfort to patient
4. Good esthetic outcome

Disadvantages:

1. Difficult in controlling the depth of deepithelialisation
2. Technique sensitive
3. Post-operative pain
4. Longer treatment time
5. High recurrence rate
6. Periodontal dressing required

Complications:

1. Harm to underlying periosteum and bone
2. Gingival recession
3. Wound healing is delayed
4. Enamel loss can occur

4. Gingivectomy technique

Dummett and Bolden in 1963 used gingivectomy to remove pigmented gums. Incisions were made to remove as much clinically pigmented tissue as possible and a surgical pack was placed. They concluded that the respective gingival procedures, if

performed purely for cosmetic reasons, would not provide any forever results. This procedure leads to prolonged wound healing by secondary intent, causing excessive pain and discomfort as the underlying bone is exposed. It also leads to non-permanent pigmentation loss. [12]

5. Bone denudation technique

Under local anaesthesia, two vertical incisions are made, one from the gingival margin to the vestibular area and extending slightly beyond the limits. The papillae are then divided into labial and lingual halves using B.P. blades. The two vertical incisions are then connected by a horizontal incision made into the vestibule apical to the pigmented band. Using a periosteal elevator, the tissue and periosteum are carefully separated from the underlying alveolar bone and removed en mass, exposing the subjacent alveolar bone. [13]

1.1.2 CRYOSURGERY

Cryosurgery is the most widely accepted method of reducing gingival pigmentation. It involves freezing the gingiva using different materials, i.e. cryogens such as liquid nitrogen at very low temperatures [14] Allington in the year 1950 was the first to use liquid nitrogen. This is a non-scarring, sutureless and dressing less method, without bleeding and causing Minimal damage to surrounding tissues. The minimum temperature required for cell damage varies depending on the cell, and melanocytes are extremely susceptible to low temperatures ranging from -4 C to -7 C, when cell death can occur. Another colourless, non-flammable, non-chlorofluorocarbon gas that is 1,1,1,2 tetrafluoroethene, often utilised which is inexpensive, simple to use, store and transport. After one week, any remaining pigmentation is often removed with a second round of cryosurgery[15] The drawbacks of this approach are post-operative edoema and difficulties in managing penetration depth.[16,17]

Advantages:

1. Easy and rapid to apply
2. Done in less time
3. No anesthesia required
4. No suturing needed
5. No bleeding encountered
6. No scar formation seen

Disadvantages:

1. Post operative swelling
2. Increased soft tissue destruction
3. Difficult to control depth of penetration

The Procedure of Cryosurgery:

Tissue type, size and depth of the lesion are used to decide the dose and delivery method. Additionally underlying structures, thickness of the epidermis, local blood flow and the water content of the skin can be considered [20]

Spray technique using spray tip:

Also known as Open-spray technique. Liquid nitrogen is filled on table top cryosurgical unit. A spray tip is selected within the border of the lesion. , no local anesthesia is required for singlr shot freeze. For large lesion 1% lignocaine is given. 1 cm away from the area and is administered at the centre of the lesion. The lesion is to thaw slowly to room temperature. The thaw time is usually double the freeze time.

The Procedure of Cryosurgery:

Tissue type, size and depth of the lesion are used to decide the dose and delivery method. Additionally underlying structures, thickness of the epidermis, local blood flow and the water content of the skin can be considered.[20]

1. Dipstick method
2. Spray technique
3. Cryoprobe technique

Cryoprobe technique:

In this method, liquid nitrogen is circulated to cool the tip of cryoprobe. Hence, freezing occurs by conduction. This technique is slower than spray technique [20]

Disadvantages:

1. Excessive tissue damage
2. Depth of penetration difficult to control
3. Burning sensation or pain
4. Stinging sensation

1.1.3 ELECTROSURGERY

In the electrosurgical procedure, heat produced by high-frequency electrical energy transmitted to the tissues causes tissue to either cut or coagulate. [18]. The use of this approach for gingival depigmentation is favoured by its ability to control bleeding, shape tissue, and produce minimal scar tissue. However, patients experience more pain and discomfort during the early healing period. With this technique[14] In addition, it requires more clinical expertise than the scalpel approach[14,16] Prolonged or repeated application can cause heat build-up and unwanted tissue destruction.[16] contact of the electrosurgical tip with the teeth, periosteum or alveolar bone can damage them.[14]

Advantages:

1. It controls hemorrhage
2. Permits adequate contouring of tissue
3. Lesser operating time
4. Less scar formation after surgery
5. Less discomfort to patient

Disadvantages:

1. More expertise required
2. More post-operative pain
3. Causes undesired tissue destruction
4. Periodontal pack required

Complications:

1. Intense inflammation occurred
2. Loss of crestal bone height seen

1.1.4 Radiosurgery

This is a new treatment modality for gingival pigmentation using radiofrequency. The thermal energy generated by the radio frequency device electrically affects the molecular breakdown of melanocytes present on the basal and supra basal layers of the gingival epithelium. The latent heat of radiosurgery delays the growth and migration of melanocytes, making it a more effective method of depigmentation than conventional method. Radiosurgery induces clotting, thereby reducing bleeding, but requires at least two treatments. Papillary areas can be easily de-pigmented with radiosurgery. Many times, the sensitivity of the technique and more cost are the limitations of this new technique [19]

It is the most advanced form of electrosurgery. It is used for removal of soft tissue with the aid of radio frequency energy. "Frequencies of 3.0 MHz (MHz) to 4.0 MHz is being used where 4.0 MHz being the optimal frequency"[20]

Advantages:

1. Produce coagulation in the treated site
2. Less thermal damage
3. Faster healing (4MHz wave technology)
4. Self-sterilising method . Little or no scar formation seen
6. Better visibility due to bloodless field

Disadvantages:

1. At least two appointment required
 2. Cannot be used in pacemaker patients
 3. Uncomfortable to patients due to foul smell
- Chemical method:
Chemical agents like 90% phenol along with 95% alcohol is used.

Disadvantages:

1. Tissue necrosis
2. Pain
3. Burn the gingiva

1.1.5 Lasers

Maiman in 1960 introduced Lasers. It is widely used in medical field. It is the most pleasant, reliable and effectivel method.

Types	Wavelength
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	(10,600 nm)
Neodymium-doped: Yttrium, Aluminum, and Garnet (Nd:YAG)	(1064 nm)
Diode	(820 nm)
Erbium (Er)-doped:YAG	(2940 nm)
Erbium- and chromium-doped: yttrium, scandium, gallium, garnet (Er,Cr:YSGG)	(2780 nm)

Advantages:

1. No periodontal dressing required
2. Minimal post-operative pain and swelling
3. Less discomfort (protein coagulum formation)
4. Blood less field (sealing nerve endings)

Disadvantages

1. Thermal damage
2. Delayed wound healing
3. Expensive treatment
4. Bone exposure and gingival fenestration can occur (21)

Diode laser:

This laser is a solid-state semiconductor that utilizes light energy from electric energy. Flexible quartz fiber optic hand piece can be used. Wavelength spectrum of 800 to 980 nm is used to absorbed by water, soft tissue and chromophores, such as oxyhemoglobin and melanin.

Advantages:

1. Good visibility
2. Excellent hemostatic agent

3. Better patient comfort
4. Less damage to periosteum and underlying bone
5. Shorter operating time

Disadvantages:

1. Slight discomfort
2. Dry and itchy feeling during procedure

Er: YAG laser:

It is manufactured with a wavelength of 2940 nm, which is ideal for absorption by water and hydroxyapatite.

Advantages:

1. Less thermal damages
2. Less pain
3. Rapid wound healing

Disadvantages:

1. Wavelength of this laser cannot absorb melanin

Nd: YAG laser:

This laser is set at 60 mJ per pulse, 6 W and 100 pulses per second. A 320 micron diameter fiber optic is used in the pigmented area with a contact mode. (20)

Advantages:

1. No complications
2. No bleeding
3. No pain

1.2 Chemical method

Chemical agents destroy the overlying epithelium in this treatment. Various chemical agents are used such as phenol, salicylic acid, glycolic acid and trichloroacetic acid. In a study by Hirschfield and Hirschfield in 1951, pigmented gums were burned by destroying tissues up to and slightly below the basal layer of mucous membranes with a mixture of 90% phenol and 95% alcohol.[40] However, re-pigmentation and relapse occurred in all cases shortly after application of either agent. Because phenol can cause cardiac arrhythmias, cardiovascular

monitoring is required. [22] The main drawback of this method is its inability to control the depth of penetration and the degree of destruction. These methods are no longer used & unacceptable to clinicians and patients alike

2.1 Free gingival graft:

Free Gingival Grafts are used extensively in root coverage procedure and to increase the width of attached gingiva. According to Tamizi, Taheri (1996), Kumar et al., 2012 and Fowler et al.(2000), a free gingival graft is required after depigmentation procedure for better esthetic outcome. It showed no evidence of repigmentation even after 4.5 years. Vikas V Pakhare et al (2017) in their case report, used free gingival autograft for treating gingival melanin hyperpigmentation and no repigmentation was seen even after 6 months.[23]

Advantages:

1. No reoccurrence
2. Esthetically appreciated

Disadvantages:

1. Second surgical site needed
2. More discomfort to patients
3. Extensive procedure
4. Poor colour matching of tissue
5. Healing is slow and painful
6. Limited donor area available

2.2 Acellular Dermal Matrix Allograft

Acellular dermal matrix allograft: Surgical blade no. 15 is used for two vertical incision on the non-pigmented tissue both mesial and distal to the pigmented area. In the pigmented area, partial thickness flap is reflected and excised by a horizontal sulcular incision. The graft is then trimmed according to the treated area and secured with sutures. This technique yields better result compared to gingival abrasion method.[25]

Advantages:

1. Less time compared to free gingival graft
2. Less post-operative discomfort
3. Less post-operative complications

Disadvantages:

1. .Clinical expertise required Expensive procedure
2. Contraction of graft can happen

Vitamin C (Ascorbic acid)

Gingival melanin pigmentation may be treated with ascorbic acid/vitamin C. [26] Tyrosine activity, which is crucial for melanin biosynthesis, is suppressed, which prevents the production of melanin.[26] Additionally, ascorbic acid directly inhibits the synthesis of dopaquinone, a precursor in the synthesis of melanin, which in turn prevents the formation of melanin. According to a study by Sheel, et al., (2015) the local application of ascorbic acid after the depigmentation treatment caused a delay in the repigmentation of gingiva [27]

A oral mesotherapy study using locally injectable Vitamin C has been known to be efficient, minimally invasive, safe and esthetically satisfactory technique for gingival depigmentation. [28]

Another novel Microneedling technique using dermapen along with the topical application of vitamin C paste has been shown to be minimally invasive, less expensive and esthetic approach for gingival hyperpigmentation. [29]

Platelet rich fibrin (PRF)

Rezmelia sari, et al., (2022), presented a case report on Topical Application of Platelet-Rich Fibrin Liquid as a Novel and Minimally Invasive Treatment to investigate post-gingival depigmentation outcomes such as wound healing, pain and post-surgical complaints after performing gingival depigmentation using surgical scalpel method. The results suggested that PRF liquid provided better post-gingival depigmentation healing than cellulose based periodontal dressings and concluded that utilization of PRF liquid is expected to be an alternative for minimally invasive open wounds management especially post-gingival depigmentation. [30]

Other advancements like application and intra-oral formulations of Kojic acid, Placenta extract are still under research.

Repigmentation based on evidence [21,23,31-37]

Kaur et al 2010	Higher reoccurrence of pigmentation in the dark-complexioned patients seen as compared to wheatish- or brown-complexioned patients in a 9 month followup.
Hegde et al 2013	Er:YAG-laser-treated sites resulted more repigmentation than the surgically or CO2-laser-treated sites
Kumar et al 2013	3 out of 10 cases showed mild areas of repigmentation on the 30th day where other 7 cases didnot show any repigmentation till 2 years.
Ribeiro et al 2014	Slight reappearance of pigmentation was found in five of the patients using Nd:YAG laser and scalpel technique
Grover et al 2014	In 11 cases, four laser and seven scalpel, a patchy repigmentation was observed at the end of 3 months
Giannelli et al 2014	Er:YAG and diode lasers gave satisfactory clinical results, with no recurrence of gingival pigmentation in a six month study.
Gupta et al 2014	7 sites in the scalpel excision group showed recurrence, whereas only 4 site showed recurrence in the electrosurgically treated group.
Basha et al 2015	Repigmentation appeared in the interdental and marginal tissues in both surgical stripping method and laser technique
Suragimath et al 2016	At the end of one year, slight melanin repigmentation was observed in three subjects treated with scalpel depigmentation procedure
Bakutra et al 2017	At 12 months followup study repigmentation is significantly lesser in surgical stripping compared to laser ablation method
Narayankar et al 2017	Recurrence of pigmentation was observed in five cases in scalpel group and two cases in TFE group in 6 month follow up
Gholami et al 2018	After 12 months, surgical stripping and Er, Cr:YSGG laser treatment techniques showed similar trends in re pigmentation where as one laser treated site, a short melanin strip recurrence seen.
Kamboj et al 2020	Repigmentation was observed in four cases out of 16 sites treated with electrocautery technique.
Chandra et al 2020	At 6 month, nearly 62.5% of cases showed postsurgical repigmentation of gingiva in both scalpel and laser techniques

REFERENCES

1. El-Shenawy H, Fahd A, Ellabban M, Dahaba M, Khalifa M. Lasers for esthetic removal of gingival hyperpigmentation: A systematic review of randomized clinical trials. *Int J Adv Res* 2017;5:1238-48.
2. Ozbayrak S, Dumlu A, Ercalik-Yalcinkaya S. Treatment of melanin pigmented gingiva and oral mucosa by CO2 laser. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod* 2000;90:14-5.
3. Malhotra S, Sharma N, Basavaraj P. Gingival esthetics by depigmentation. *J Periodontal Med Clin Pract* 2014;1:79-84.
4. Roshni T, Nandakumar K. Anterior Esthetic Gingival depigmentation and crown lengthening: Report of a case. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2005;6(3):139-47
5. Malhotra S, Sharma N, Basavaraj P. Gingival esthetics by depigmentation. *J Periodontal Med Clin Pract.* 2014;1:79-84.
6. Roshni T, Nandakumar K. Anterior Esthetic Gingival depigmentation and crown lengthening: Report of a case. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2005;6(3):139-47
7. Grover HS, Dadlani H, Bhardwaj A, Yadav A, Lal S. Evaluation of patient response and recurrence of pigmentation following gingival depigmentation using laser and scalpel technique: A clinical study. *J Indian Soc Periodontol* 2014;18:586-92.
8. Dummett CO, Gupta OP. Estimating the epidemiology of oral pigmentation. *J Natl Med Assoc* 1964;56:419-20
9. Dey SM, Nagarathna DV, Jacob C, Roy JS. Split Mouth Gingival Depigmentation with Scalpel and Diode Laser. A Comparative Study.
10. Hirschfeld I, Hirschfeld L. Oral pigmentation and method of removing it. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Path.* 1951;4:1012-1012.
11. Malhotra S, Sharma N, Basavaraj P. Gingival esthetics by depigmentation. *J Periodontal Med Clin Pract.* 2014;1:79-84.
12. Dummett CO. Oral pigmentation. First symposium of oral pigmentation. *J Periodontol.* 1960;31(5):356-60. doi:10.1902/jop. 1960.31.5.345.
13. Yeh CJ. Cryosurgical management of melanin pigmented gingival. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 1998;86:660- 63.
14. Moneim RA, El Deeb M, Rabea AA. Gingival pigmentation (cause, treatment and histological preview). *Future Dent J* 2017;3:1-7.
15. Stabholz A, Zeltser R, Sela M, Peretz B, Moshonov J, Ziskind D, et al. The use of lasers in dentistry: principles of operation and clinical applications. *Compend Contin Educ Dent.* 2003;24(12):935-48.
16. Prasad SS, Agrawal N, Reddy NR. Gingival depigmentation: A Case report. *People's J Sci Res* 2010;3:27-30.
17. Almas K, Sadig W. Surgical treatment of melanin-pigmented gingiva; an esthetic approach. *Indian J Dent Res* 2002;13:70-3.
18. Gupta ND, Agrawal A, Agrawal N, Yadav P. Gingival depigmentation by different technique: A case series. *IOSR J Dent Med Sci* 2015;14:93-7.
19. Mahesh HV, Harish MR, Shashikumar BM, Ramya KS. Gingival pigmentation reduction: A novel therapeutic modality. *J Cutan Aesthet Surg* 2012;5:137-40
20. Abdel Moneim R et al. Gingival pigmentation (cause, treatment and histological preview). *Future Dental Journal.* 2017;3(1):1-7.

21. Gul M et al. Most effective method for the management of physiologic gingival hyperpigmentation: A systematic review and metaanalysis. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2019;23(3):203
22. Kathariya R, Pradeep AR. Split mouth de-epithelization techniques for gingival depigmentation: A case series and review of literature. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2011 Apr;15(2):161-8. Pubmed PMID: 21976842.
23. Giannelli M et al. Comparative Evaluation of Photoablative Efficacy of Erbium: Yttrium Aluminium-Garnet and Diode Laser for the Treatment of Gingival Hyperpigmentation. A Randomized Split-Mouth Clinical Trial. *Journal of Periodontology.* 2014;85(4):554–61
24. Spinell T, Tarnow D. Restoring lost gingival pigmentation in the esthetic zone: A case report. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2015 Jun;146(6):402-5. Pubmed PMID: 26025828.
25. Pakhare V et al. Gingival depigmentation by free gingival autograft: a case series. *Dental Update.* 2017;2;44(2):158–62.
26. Shimada Y, Tai H, Tanaka A, Ikezawa-Suzuki I, Takagi K, Yoshida Y, et al. Effects of ascorbic acid on gingival melanin pigmentation in vitro and in vivo. *J Periodontol* 2009; 80:317-23.
27. Sheel V, Purwar P, Dixit J, Rai P. Ancillary role of vitamin C in pink aesthetics. *BMJ Case Rep* 2015;2015: pii: bcr2014208559.
28. . Dawar A, Kamra P, Anand D, Nayyar V, Mishra D, Pandey S. *Quintessence Int.* 2022 Jun 20;53(7):580-588.
29. Rezmelia Sari and Abizar Agung Wibawa, (2022), “Topical Application of Platelet-Rich Fibrin Liquid as a Novel and Minimally Invasive Treatment for Post-Gingival Depigmentation: A Case Report” in *The International Online Seminar Series on Periodontology in conjunction with Scientific Seminar, KnE Medicine*, pages 190–199. DOI 10.18502/kme.v 2i1.10851.
30. El-Shenawy H, Fahd A, Ellabban M, Dahaba M, Khalifa M. Lasers for esthetic removal of gingival hyperpigmentation: A systematic review of randomized clinical trials. *Int J Adv Res* 2017;5: 1238 48.
31. Basha M et al. Comparison of Nd:YAG Laser and Surgical Stripping for Treatment of Gingival Hyperpigmentation: A Clinical Trial. *Photomedicine and Laser Surgery.* 2015;33(8):424–36.
32. Suragimath G et al. A Split Mouth Randomized Clinical Comparative Study to Evaluate the Efficacy of Gingival Depigmentation Procedure Using Conventional Scalpel Technique or Diode Laser. *J Lasers Med Sci.* 2016;27;7(4):227–32.
33. Bakutra G et al. Comparative evaluation of diode laser ablation and surgical stripping technique for gingival depigmentation: A clinical and immunohistochemical study. *International Journal of Health Sciences.* 2017;11(2):8.
34. Narayankar S et al. Comparative evaluation of gingival depigmentation by tetrafluroethane cryosurgery and surgical scalpel technique. A randomized clinical study. *Contemp Clin Dent.* 2017;8(1):90.
35. Gholami L et al. Comparison of gingival depigmentation with Er,Cr:YSGG laser and surgical stripping, a 12-month follow-up. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2018 Nov;33(8):1647–56.
36. Kamboj S, Salaria S. Efficacy of liquid nitrogen and electrocautery assisted gingival depigmentation in term of patient’s perception, histological wound healing - A randomized triple blind clinical trial. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2020;24(2):135.

37. Chandra G et al. Evaluation of surgical scalpel versus semiconductor diode laser techniques in the management of gingival melanin hyperpigmentation: A split-mouth randomized clinical comparative study. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2020;24(1):47